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A review paper re-submitted to Biotechnology Advances

Insights into microbial diversity in wastewater treatment systems: How far have we come?

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ABSTRACT

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Biological wastewater treatment processes are based on the exploitation of the concerted activity of microorganisms. Knowledge on the microbial community structure and the links to the changing environmental conditions is therefore crucial for the development and optimization of biological systems by engineers. The advent of molecular techniques occurred in the last decades quickly showed the inadequacy of culture-dependent methodologies to unveil the great level of diversity present in sludge samples. Initially, culture-independent technologies and more recently the application of *-omics* in wastewater microbiology, has drawn a new view of microbial diversity and function of wastewater treatment systems. This article reviews the current knowledge on the topic placing emphasis on crucial microbial processes carried out in biological wastewater treatment systems driven by specific groups of microbes, such as nitrogen and phosphorus removal bacteria, filamentous and electrogenic microorganisms, as well as Archaea. Despite the recent *-omics* has offered substantial insights into the diversity and ecophysiology of these bacteria never envisioned before by providing millions of sequence reads at an unprecedented scale, studies based on high-throughput sequencing are still scarce. In order to obtain significant gains in the analysis of structure-function relationships, a greater sequencing investment is needed, particularly to uncover gene expression patterns of functionally relevant genes.

Keywords: molecular techniques, wastewater microbiology, *-omics*, nitrogen removal, phosphorus removal, electrogenic bacteria, archaea, bulking

51 **1. Introduction**

52 Through the history of mankind, water availability has played an essential role in
53 human development. In this sense, global demand for water has been continuously
54 rising due to population growth and increasing socioeconomic activities; in a hundred
55 years the world population has tripled while water consumption has increased six-fold.
56 This circumstance is particularly critical in areas where deficiency in hydric resources
57 prevails, a situation that has prompted the need for wastewater treatment and
58 subsequent reuse. The quantity and quality of waste generated and discharged into
59 natural water bodies is a topic of serious concern in our world today, and the wealthiest
60 nations invest a considerable effort for mitigating the pollution of dense populations (Oh
61 et al., 2010). In this context, knowledge of the wastewater source is fundamental to
62 determine its physical, chemical and biological characteristics and to establish an
63 appropriate treatment strategy. Composition of wastewaters depends on their origin but
64 in general, major contaminants found include organic compounds, xenobiotics, metals,
65 suspended soils, nutrients (mainly nitrogen and phosphorus) and pathogenic
66 microorganisms (Bitton, 2005). Depending on the final use of the water (drinking,
67 recreation, irrigation, etc), several technologies can apply to remove these compounds.
68 Among them, biological wastewater treatment systems rely on the use of
69 microorganisms; the unique abilities of microbes to degrade organic matter, remove
70 nutrients and transform toxic compounds into harmless products makes them the
71 essential players in waste removal.

72 For a century, biological wastewater treatment plants (BWWTPs) based in activated
73 sludge have been in charge of treating both domestic and industrial wastes and have
74 constituted an essential instrument in environmental protection. Initially, by the end of
75 the nineteenth century, removal of organic matter and suspended soils was the main
76 requirement, but nowadays BWWTPs have additional objectives, such as elimination of
77 toxic metals, odors, nutrients (N, P) and pathogens (Bitton, 2005). However, a
78 drawback of this technology is the high performance costs, given the need for aeration
79 as well as moving biomass between treatment tanks (Oh et al., 2010; Sheik et al.,
80 2014). Additionally, powerful greenhouse gases such as CH₄ and N₂O are generated in
81 BWWTPs (Sheik et al., 2014). Giving an answer to this problem, Sheik et al. (2014)
82 proposed a bottom-up design approach for BWWTPs based in the concept of
83 “wastewater biorefinery column”, which relies on the engineering of distinct ecological
84 niches to guarantee the targeted enrichment of specific functional groups for
85 sustainable production of bioenergy, bioplastic and fertilizers.

86 Currently, besides BWWTPs, other ecologically engineered systems are becoming
87 alternative solutions to conventional processes due to their efficiency, low
88 establishment costs and low operation and management requirements. Under the
89 denomination of non-conventional technologies, different strategies can be
90 distinguished. For instance, green filters use land planted with trees flooded with the
91 wastewater to be treated; purification is the result of physical, chemical and biological
92 factors (Fahd et al., 2007). Also, constructed wetlands are passive treatment systems
93 constituted by lagoons or shallow ponds or channels planted with characteristic
94 wetland vegetation (aquatic macrophytes), which mimic natural wetlands under a more
95 controlled environment. Different categories of constructed wetlands exist according
96 mainly to hydrology (open water-surface flow and subsurface flow), type of macrophytic
97 growth (emerged, submerged, free-floating) and flow path (horizontal and vertical)
98 (Vymazal, 2011). Other constructed systems simulate the natural processes of
99 purification that occur in rivers and lakes (Middelbrooks et al., 1982) or are based on
100 wastewater filtration through beds using peat (Couillard, 1994) or sand (Lian et al.,
101 2014). An additional sustainable option that has gained thrust in the last decade
102 includes the use of microbial fuel cells (MFCs), i.e. bioelectrochemical systems where
103 bacteria oxidize organic compounds and the electrons generated in this process are

104 converted into electrical energy (Kelly and He, 2014; Mathuriya et al., 2014). The
105 energy produced from wastewater treatment could recover the cost of the process, a
106 promising perspective for this alternative.

107 A variety of lab-scale systems, such as particulate biofilm reactors or membrane
108 bioreactors (MBR) among others, have also been used as pilot systems for wastewater
109 treatment (Ballesteros Martín et al., 2011; Nicolella et al., 2000). They have the
110 advantage of being compact and well-controlled systems with small area requirements
111 which minimize the excess of sludge production; they can also maintain a high
112 biomass age (of several weeks), while the high biomass concentration and mass
113 transfer area result in high conversion capacities to specifically degrade key pollutants.
114 Besides, they have the advantage that changes in the design can be made more
115 economically. However, biofilm formation on carriers can lead to long start-up times,
116 and scaling-up from laboratory scale reactors to full-scale applications exhibit some
117 unknown aspects, since it is difficult to predict the behaviour of a complex process
118 (Nicolella et al., 2000).

119 In all these technologies, performance of the wastewater treatment process is based
120 on the exploitation of the concerted activity of the microorganisms involved. Knowledge
121 on the microbial community structure and the links to the changing environmental
122 conditions is therefore crucial for the development and optimization of biological
123 systems by engineers. Before the development of cultivation-independent techniques,
124 the key drivers of pollutant removal processes were hardly known. This scenario
125 overturned in the last decade of the 20th century with the development of a suite of
126 molecular methods that allowed the study of these organisms circumventing cultivation.
127 Further, the *-omics* revolution occurred in the last years has boosted our
128 understanding on the biology of these biotechnological processes. In this review, we
129 provide an outline on the current scene of the diversity and genomics of prokaryotes in
130 various wastewater treatment systems highlighting the findings of some crucial
131 microbial processes in this field and discussing some unresolved questions.

132

133 **2. Approaches to study wastewater microbiology**

134 The advent of molecular methods such as Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR)
135 techniques revolutionized the study of microbial diversity previously constrained by our
136 inability to grow the majority of microorganisms in culture (Rappé and Giovannoni,
137 2003). PCR amplification and sequencing (Fig. 1) have been used now for decades to
138 study the presence, diversity and expression of ribosomal and protein-coding genes in
139 these constructed environments, allowing the identification of the key microorganisms
140 involved in processes such as carbon-degrading and ammonia oxidation (Gilbride et
141 al., 2006; Wagner and Loy, 2002). These PCR approaches shed light on the diversity
142 of main players in BWWTPs and how genetic diversity is structured in relation to
143 certain environmental parameters (Wang et al., 2012; Wells et al., 2011). Yet, there are
144 inherent PCR amplification- and primer-related biases that limit the quantitative
145 information that can be extracted from these approaches. Perhaps the most critical
146 step from these is primer design, which may be remarkably challenging for the highly
147 diverse functional genes. However, fluorescent in situ hybridization (FISH) using group-
148 specific rRNA-targeted oligonucleotide probes circumvents the PCR bias and has been
149 largely applied to wastewater microbiology providing quantitative information on the
150 dominant groups involved in the different processes of waste removal (Joss et al.,
151 2011; Nielsen et al., 2009b; Wagner et al., 1996).

152 After the initial application of these approaches, the rise of the “*-omics* era” has
153 resulted in a turning point in studying phylogenetic and functional diversity of
154 wastewater treatment systems (Fig. 1). The development of the so-called High
155 Throughput Sequencing (HTS) techniques, i.e., 454-pyrosequencing and Illumina

156 among others, has allowed producing millions of sequence reads at an unimaginable
157 low cost. Whole genome sequencing of isolated microorganisms was the first step
158 taken to elucidate the functional potential of wastewater relevant microorganisms
159 (Table 1). Beyond the initial genome sequencing of cultures, metagenomics (the
160 massive DNA sequencing of all genes present in a microbial community) and
161 metatranscriptomics (sequencing of all genes being transcribed, and therefore, likely
162 expressed in a microbial community) have been applied to unveil the genomic potential
163 and transcripts of whole microbial communities circumventing isolation and PCR
164 (Venter et al., 2004; Yu and Zhang, 2012). However, these approaches have also the
165 limitation that most of the information is derived from the most abundant members of
166 the community. Despite treatment systems present in general less diversity than
167 natural ecosystems, significant gains in the analysis of gene expression patterns
168 require a greater sequencing investment and the combination of both metagenomics
169 and metatranscriptomics, but these studies are still rare (Yu and Zhang, 2012). More
170 effort is needed to understand the functional capabilities of microbial communities in
171 wastewater treatments and what genes are expressed under which circumstances to
172 better understand the relationship between structure and function in these microbially-
173 mediated processes.

174 In addition to nucleic acid based methods, the study of metaproteomics (Fig. 1) can
175 lead to the identification of proteins involved in known processes and also to the
176 discovery of unrecognized metabolic processes and functional roles, since there are
177 still many protein families whose function is unknown. Gene sequence similarity does
178 not necessarily reflect functional conservation and simple modifications can lead to
179 major modifications on the activity and the specificity of the corresponding enzyme
180 (Ufarté et al., 2015). A recent metaproteomics pilot study allowed the identification of
181 most proteins involved in glycolysis, citrate cycle and nitrogen removal in a wastewater
182 treatment plant (Püttker et al., 2015). Metabolomics (the analysis of all cellular
183 metabolites) is perhaps currently the least used field of the *-omics* approaches
184 primarily due to analytical complexity but it is clear that its emergence will be critical to
185 understand microbe–microbe and microbe–molecule interactions.

186 Despite the potential of *-omics* for studying functional capabilities within a microbial
187 community, the power of culturing individual species cannot be neglected. Cultures
188 have provided the basis for our understanding of the microbial world and are necessary
189 for physiological studies in a simplified and controlled environment. These studies are
190 crucial to interpret *-omics* data and to ascertain the relevance of the newly discovered
191 functions of proteins through *-omics*. Until recently, culturing was also necessary to
192 generate reference genomes, but access to the genome of uncultured organisms is
193 nowadays granted thanks to the development of single-cell sorting and manipulation
194 and whole-genome amplification (SAGs) (Fig. 1) (Blainey, 2013; Dichosa et al., 2015).
195 However, despite of the enormous advances gained on knowledge of the identity and
196 function of wastewater microorganisms, we are still far from reaching a full
197 understanding of these largely complex microbial communities. The combination of all
198 these approaches with systematic measurements and experimental validation (eco-
199 systems biology) will be the path to achieve a holistic characterization of microbial
200 consortia responsible for waste treatment (Narayanasamy et al., 2015).

201

202 **Table 1. Some examples of wastewater relevant microorganisms for which sequencing projects**
 203 **have been completed**

Process	Organism	Reference and/or Genbank Accession Number
Carbon and toxic compounds removal	<i>Aminomonas paucivorans</i>	Pitluck et al., 2010; NZ_AEIV00000000
	<i>Anaerobaculum mobile</i>	Mavromatis et al., 2013; NC_018024
	<i>Arthrobacter nitroguajacolicus</i>	Niewerth et al., 2012; BBFS00000000
	<i>Cloacibacillus evryensis</i>	NZ_JFBR00000000
	<i>Comamonas testosteroni</i>	Fukuda et al., 2014; CP006704
	<i>Cand. Competibacter denitrificans</i>	NZ_CBTJ020000020
	<i>Can. Contendobacter odensis</i>	NZ_CBTk000000000
	<i>Exiguobacterium alkaliphilum</i>	NZ_JJMw01000019
	<i>Methanocorpusculum labreanum</i>	Anderson et al., 2009; CP000559
	<i>Methanofollis liminatans</i>	NZ_AGCO00000000
	<i>Methanolinea tarda</i>	Yamamoto et al., 2014; AGIY02000000
	<i>Pseudomonas moraviensis</i>	Hunter et al., 2014; AYMZ00000000
	<i>Pseudomonas otitidis</i>	NZ_JGYF01000080
	<i>Pseudomonas stutzeri</i>	Busquets et al., 2013; AMVM01000000
	<i>Rhodococcus ruber</i>	Shumkova et al., 2015; LDUF01000000
<i>Sediminibacterium</i> sp.	Ayarza et al., 2014; AXUM01000000	
<i>Sphingomonas</i> sp.	Chen et al., 2014; JMUB00000000	
<i>Thauera</i> sp.	Dichosa et al., 2015; JTDM01000000	
Nitrogen removal		
Ammonia oxidation	<i>Nitrosomonas europaea</i>	Chain et al., 2013; AL954747
	<i>Nitrosomonas eutropha</i>	Stein et al., 2007; CP000450
Nitrite oxidation	<i>Nitrobacter hamburgensis</i>	Starkenburger et al., 2008; CP000319
	<i>Nitrobacter winogradskyi</i>	Starkenburger et al., 2006; CP000115
	<i>Nitrospina gracilis</i>	Lücker et al., 2013; NZ_CAQJ01000000
	' <i>Cand. Nitrospira defluvii</i> '	Lücker et al., 2010; GCA_000196815.1
Denitrification	<i>Paracoccus denitrificans</i>	Siddavattam et al., 2011; CP002897
	<i>Thiobacillus denitrificans</i>	Beller et al., 2006; CP000116
Anammox	' <i>Cand. Kuenenia stuttgartiensis</i> '	Strous et al., 2006; CT030148
Phosphorus removal		
	<i>Gemmatimonas aurantiaca</i>	AP009153
	' <i>Cand. Accumulibacter phosphatis</i> '	Mao et al., 2014; NC_013194.1
	<i>Tetrasphaera jenkinsii</i>	Kristiansen et al., 2013; NZ_HF571038

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205 **3. Microbial diversity in wastewater treatment systems**

206 Initial description of the microbial structure in a variety of treatment systems was
 207 conducted in the last decades through the application of culture-independent
 208 techniques such as DGGE (Adrados et al., 2014; Ballesteros Martín et al., 2011; Boon
 209 et al., 2002), T-RFLP (Eschenhagen et al., 2003; Hiraishi et al., 2000; Wang et al.,
 210 2011), cloning (Sánchez et al., 2011; Snaird et al., 1997; Vainio et al., 1997), and
 211 particularly FISH (Kämpfer et al., 1996; Manz et al., 1994; Sánchez et al., 2011;
 212 Wagner et al., 1994; Wallner et al., 1995). Concerning activated sludge, perhaps the
 213 most commonly used technology for treating sewage, these studies highlighted the
 214 dominance of the phylum Proteobacteria, followed by other groups (like Bacteroidetes,
 215 Chloroflexi, Actinobacteria, Planctomycetes, Firmicutes, etc) in different proportions

216 depending on the conditions (Boon et al., 2002; Snaidr et al., 1997; Wagner et al.,
217 1994; Wang et al., 2011). These observations have been confirmed when further high
218 throughput techniques (HTS) were applied (Ju et al., 2014; Kwon et al., 2010;
219 Sanapareddy et al., 2009; Sánchez et al., 2013). Furthermore, HTS allowed the
220 identification of groups that had remained undetected with the former molecular
221 methods, deepening our information on the diversity of activated sludge. Additionally,
222 metagenomic studies pointed out to the dominance of functional categories involved in
223 carbohydrates, protein metabolism and amino acids derivatives (Ju et al., 2014) or the
224 metabolism of aromatic compounds (Sanapareddy et al., 2009). On the other hand,
225 these new methodologies confirmed that members of the Domain Bacteria are largely
226 responsible for the majority of carbon removal (Sánchez et al., 2011; Yu and Zhang,
227 2012) while Archaea seem to be less relevant.

228 Proteobacteria also showed to be dominant in other wastewater treatment
229 processes such as constructed wetlands, although other groups as Bacteroidetes,
230 Actinobacteria, Firmicutes, Chloroflexi or Acidobacteria were retrieved in some
231 samples with fingerprinting methods (Adrados et al., 2014; Sidrach-Cardona et al.,
232 2015). In these engineered systems, microbial communities appeared to be mainly
233 affected by hydraulic configuration and plant presence, as well as organic load in a
234 lesser extend. Pyrosequencing analyses of different types of constructed wetlands
235 showed a wider range of phyla involved in wastewater treatment besides those
236 mentioned above, for instance, Verrucomicrobia, Planctomycetes, Nitrospirae,
237 Cyanobacteria, TM7 or Gemmatimonadetes among others (Ansola et al., 2014; Arroyo
238 et al., 2015; Zhao et al., 2015a; Zhong et al., 2015). These results were confirmed with
239 recent metagenomic analyses (Bai et al., 2014). In any case, all these studies have
240 reasserted the predominance of Proteobacteria.

241

242 **4. Microorganisms involved in nitrogen removal**

243 Nitrification and denitrification constitute key processes in wastewater treatment
244 because they are considered the major mechanisms of nitrogen (N) removal. Ammonia
245 and nitrite are toxic to aquatic life and can also contribute to eutrophication of receiving
246 waters. It is known that ammonia oxidation can be performed by aerobic and anaerobic
247 oxidizers, which include the proteobacterial ammonia oxidizers (AOB) and the
248 anaerobic ammonia oxidation (anammox) bacteria (Fig. 2). The proteobacterial
249 ammonia oxidizers, which can carry out aerobic or anaerobic ammonia oxidation
250 depending on oxygen concentration (Schmidt et al., 2003), include two monophyletic
251 groups, the Betaproteobacteria ammonia oxidizers *Nitrosomonas* and *Nitrosospira*, and
252 the Gammaproteobacteria *Nitrosococcus* (with the exception of *Nitrosococcus mobilis*,
253 a beta-proteobacterium lineage); under oxic conditions, the main product from their
254 metabolism is nitrite, while dinitrogen, nitrite and nitric oxide are produced under anoxic
255 conditions. On the other hand, anammox, a novel and promising biotechnological
256 process for nitrogen removal from ammonia to nitrogen gas, is mediated by a
257 monophyletic group of bacteria within the phylum Planctomycetes; it includes five
258 genera identified by culture-independent techniques (*Candidatus* 'Brocadia',
259 *Candidatus* 'Kuenenia', *Candidatus* 'Scalindua', *Candidatus* 'Anammoxoglobus' and
260 *Candidatus* 'Jettenia') (Fig. 2) (Ali et al., 2013; Hu et al., 2011).

261 Additionally, other heterotrophic bacteria (Kim et al., 2005) and some Archaea
262 (AOA) have been reported to oxidize ammonia (You et al., 2009). Although little
263 attention has been paid to the role of Archaea in wastewater treatment processes, the
264 results obtained comparing the abundance of AOB and AOA (now classified within the
265 phylum Thaumarchaeota) (Brochier-Armanet et al., 2008; Spang et al., 2010) by
266 means of molecular methods are controversial, since some studies report either the
267 complete absence of AOA (Mußmann et al., 2011; Yu and Zhang, 2012), a minimal or

268 equal contribution (Jin et al., 2010; Sonthiphand et al., 2011; Wells et al., 2009;
269 Yapsakli et al., 2011), or a dominance of AOA over AOB (Bai et al., 2012; Kayee et al.,
270 2011; Sauder et al., 2012). Thus, no clear conclusion can be drawn from these studies
271 about the role of Archaea in ammonia oxidation and therefore, more studies are
272 needed to ascertain under which circumstances they play a significant role.

273 Nitrification implies also a second oxidative step from nitrite to nitrate (nitrite
274 oxidation), which is performed by the aerobic nitrite bacteria (NOB) and traditionally
275 comprise members of the genera *Nitrobacter* (Alphaproteobacteria), *Nitrococcus*
276 (Gammaproteobacteria) and *Nitrospira* (Nitrospirae) (Wagner et al., 2002). However,
277 little is known about their diversity and ecological niche differentiation in complex
278 communities. In a recent study combining different molecular techniques, Gruber-
279 Dorninger and colleagues (2015) revealed the presence of diverse *Nitrospira* clusters
280 with functional differences concerning the preferred nitrite concentration, the use of
281 formate and the spatial co-aggregation with other AOB; they also reported the
282 presence of as many as 121 species-level *nrxB* (encoding the beta subunit of nitrite
283 oxidoreductase) operational taxonomic units of *Nitrospira*, showing an unusual high
284 diversity not documented before.

285 In the last years, molecular techniques such as DGGE, cloning, tag sequencing,
286 metagenomics or FISH, or a combination of some of them, have shed light in the
287 identification of the microorganisms involved in nitrogen removal through nitrification in
288 wastewater treatment systems. Table 2 offers a description of the main nitrifiers (AOB
289 and NOB) identified in activated sludge samples, as well as in non-conventional
290 engineered systems. Some of these systems are dominated by a single ammonia or
291 nitrite oxidizer species, while others harbor different populations. *Nitrosomonas* sp.
292 appears to be virtually present in all the systems described, as well as the NOB
293 *Nitrospira*. Overall, the results confirm the presence of the already described AOB and
294 NOB in previous works, but also, other not so common genera, such as *Nitrosovibrio* or
295 *Nitrospina* and *Nitrotoga* were found.

296 Denitrification, the transformation of nitrate or nitrite into gaseous forms (N_2 and
297 N_2O), is an ability dispersed in diverse phylogenetic lineages. Different
298 chemoorganotrophic, lithoautotrophic, and phototrophic bacteria, as well as some
299 Archaea and fungi, can perform this process (Zumft, 1997). It is essentially a facultative
300 trait, triggered by environmental parameters such as oxygen reduced conditions and
301 availability of a nitrogen oxide. Similarly to other groups, molecular techniques have
302 proved to be valuable for the study of the structure and function of wastewater
303 denitrification communities (Lu et al., 2014). The genera *Alcaligenes*, *Pseudomonas*,
304 *Methylobacterium*, *Bacillus*, *Paracoccus*, *Hyphomicrobium*, as well as members of the
305 order Rhodocyclales among others are able to carry out denitrification (Hosselhoe et
306 al., 2009; Wagner et al. 2002; Zumft, 1997). Recently, genomic analyses have
307 revealed novel processes concerning non-conventional types of denitrification (Isobe
308 and Ohte, 2014). For example, some microorganisms, such as *Candidatus*
309 *Methylomirabilis oxyfera*, could couple the formation of N_2 with the anaerobic oxidation
310 of CH_4 (Ettwig et al., 2010), and non-denitrifying species, like *Anaeromixobacter*
311 *dehalogenans*, could catalyze the reduction of N_2O to N_2 by means of an atypical
312 nitrous oxide reductase (Sanford et al., 2012).

313 Furthermore, recent metagenomic studies in a laboratory-scale sequencing batch
314 reactor (SBR) treating artificial wastewater have offered new insights into the
315 simultaneous removal of nitrogen and organic carbon with the coupling of anammox,
316 denitrification and dissimilatory nitrate reduction to ammonium (Shu et al., 2015).
317 Metagenomics was also useful to explore microbial community composition and
318 potential function in a constructed wetland (Bai et al., 2014), where nitrification and
319 denitrification were the main transformation processes in the N cycle, highlighting the
320 major role of microbes on the removal of nutrients and contaminants from wastewater.

Figure

